

PREDICTION OF PERCEIVED IMAGE QUALITY BY MOBILE DEVICE USERS

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Abstract

This paper provides an overview of the PhD research of perceived image quality (PIQ) assessment, which has a great potential for image processing in many applications. The outcome of this research can be used by smartphone vendors in order to shorten “time to market,” or by any image quality experts, particularly in the academia, to reduce the time and cost of PIQ assessment of smartphones with a small high-definition display. The method can be implemented in a software if it is embedded in the social network websites to predict and improve the image quality as perceived by the users in real time. The research was based on no reference (NR) PIQ evaluation experiments combined with the VIQET software application. The experiments include human visual tests (HVTs) for subjective image quality assessment. The results of HVTs analysis identify the most effective image quality attributes for perceived image quality. The VIQET software tool was calibrated according to the HVTs scores.

1. Introduction

Digital imaging and image-processing technologies have revolutionized the way in which we capture, store, receive, view, utilize, and share images. Social network websites, such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Snapchat, and other social media as well as the huge growth of smartphones, have become a significant part of our everyday lives. Worldwide, people of all ages capture photos and immediately upload them to social networks. Nearly 80% of social media time is now spent on mobile devices (Fig. 1).

The massive transportation of photos and videos in social networks occurs regardless of the material image quality. The main outcome of research is a new zero, or no reference (NR) subjective quality assessment model and framework that would enable the smartphone industry prediction of the PIQ. However, this quantitative method based on combination of results of HVTs with image analysis by VIQET [2] can be used for real time image quality improvement in social networks.

Fig. 1. Percentage of global digital snapshot [1].

Figure 2 shows a new proposed framework for real time image quality assessment and image quality improvement. Where images captured by smartphones uploaded to the social network website, the image goes first through the embedded software for real time image quality evaluation and improvement, and vice versa then it is loaded into the server.

Fig. 2. Real time image quality evaluation and improvement.

The first half of this paper provides the discussion of the framework of evaluation and prediction of NR perceived image quality, utilized methods, and provided experiments. The second half of this paper proves the results of PIQ assessment model. The goal of this study is to help practitioners and researchers to keep abreast of the recent advances in PIQ assessment, which can be embedded as software in many online applications, such as social networks, and many portable devices with small high-definition display, such as smartphones, phablets, and tablet PCs.

2. Perceived Image Quality Assessment Framework

a. Selected image quality attributes for PIQ

Most of the standard image quality factors (sharpness, noise, dynamic range (exposure range), tone reproduction, contrast, color accuracy, distortion, artifacts, etc.) have been considered by researchers as important factors to IQ assessment. In this work, only four standard IQ attributes were selected: brightness, sharpness, contrast, and color saturation. With this reduced number of IQ attributes, there are several important issues to consider, such as the relationship of these IQAs to other IQ criteria used in IQ evaluation applications.

With this intention, the IQ attributes should be based on perception and measurement for technological IQ issues. The IQ attributes should be sufficiently clear to be scored by observers. In addition, the standard IQ attributes should be suitable for other IQ metrics using different IQ criteria. The existing groups of standard IQ attributes and IQ assessment models do not fulfill all of these requirements; therefore, a new group of IQ attributes is needed for HVTs and IQ assessment by software application.

Many of the IQ attributes used in research are similar and have common contribution to the perceived IQ [3–5]. This feature enables them to be grouped within more general IQ attributes in order to create a simpler evaluation of perceived IQ. There is usually a compromise between the simplicity of the IQ assessment procedure and the accuracy when it comes to human visual test performance.

The image quality circle [10] in Fig. 3 describes the link between the customer quality preference and the imaging system. This circle clearly works; however, it is inefficient over time because a new data collection effort is required every time a parameter is changed. The four elements of the PIQ approach are as follows: brightness, contrast, color saturation, and sharpness.

In this research, these attributes have been extracted to more reliable IQ attributes to be used by VIQET.

Fig. 3. Image quality circle [10] and the new approach with VIQET.

b. The actual PIQ process in industry

The flow chart in Fig. 4 illustrates the actual procedure for PIQ assessment of smartphones and the new approach implemented in PhD research. This process was performed in the vendors IQ labs by image quality experts; then, they perform subjective IQ assessment through visual experiments, while the observers are “non-experts” in image quality. The obtained results make it possible to correlate the objective assessment results with the subjective assessment results through relationships between classic IQAs and VIQET IQAs.

Image quality can be characterized according to perceptual attributes from various perspectives; however, the selection of the most important image quality attributes has different priorities in different research domains. This research brings special attentions to brightness, contrast, colors, and sharpness by utilizing the proposed image quality assessment framework [8, 9]. Hence, the classic IQAs were extracted to the VIQET application IQ categories as described in Table 1.

Table 1. Image quality attribute extraction to VIQET image quality categories

Image quality attributes	VIQET image quality categories
Brightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illumination • % Over-exposed • % Under-exposed • Lux
Contrast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic range+-
Color	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Saturation • Color warmth
Sharpness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-scale edge acutance • Multi-scale texture acutance • Noise signature index

Fig. 4. Old and new PIQ assessment processes.

c. Image quality analysis by VIQET

VIQET is an objective NR IQ evaluation tool. It estimates an overall MOS (MOS range 1 to 5, while 1 = “poor” and 5 = “excellent”) for tested images. The estimated MOS for each image is based on a number of image quality categories and statistics extracted from the test photo.

The images tested by VIQET and MOS_p were calculated and analyzed; the VIQET parameters were modified according to the relationship between IQAs and VIQET categories.

The flow chart of the process of IQ assessment using the VIQET is illustrated in Fig. 5. In that process, the VIQET IQ categories were calibrated simultaneously according to the results of HVTs of PIQ. This process ended as the VIQET scores were well correlated with the HVTs scores. The next step will be the evaluation of the VIQET capabilities in prediction of PIQ.

Fig. 5. Image quality assessment by VIQET.

d. Credibility of the PIQ prediction by VIQET

After the subjective tests, the credibility of VIQET in PIQ assessment was checked using the process suggested by ITU-T recommendation P.913 [7]:

(a) *Linear Pearson correlation coefficient* (Eq. (2.1)): Measures the linear relationship between a model’s performance and the subjective data. A significant advantage is that it is on a standard comprehensible scale of –1 to 1 and has been used frequently in similar testing.

The value obtained in this research was 0.86; it shows a high correlation between HVTs’ scores and VIQET’ scores.

The LPCC is calculated as follows:

$$LPCC = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X}) * (Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum (X_i - \bar{X})^2} * \sqrt{\sum (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}} \tag{2.1}$$

X_i denotes the subjective score $MOS(i)$ in HVT for the processed image (IQ attribute added), X denotes the MOS (“objective”) of the processed image (IQ attribute added), Y_i denotes the subjective score $MOSp(i)$ in HVT of the original image (no IQ attribute added), and Y denotes the MOS (“objective”) of the original image. N in equation (2.2) represents the total number of images considered in the analysis.

Root Mean Square Error (Eq. (2.2)): The accuracy of the objective metric is evaluated using the RMSE evaluation metric:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_N P_{error}[i]^2 \right)} \tag{2.2}$$

where N denotes the total number of images considered in the analysis. The accuracy and signification of the MOS results of the subjective IQ assessment during the visual test sessions were examined using the RMSE formula.

(b) *Calculating difference of MOS values (DMOS)*: The data analysis was performed using the DMOS values calculated for each IQ attribute. DMOS values were calculated using the following formula:

$$DMOS = MOS_{iq} - MOS_o \tag{2.3}$$

where MOS_{iq} is the average of MOS of IQ attribute and MOS_o is the average of MOS of the original image. In using this formula, higher DMOS values indicate better quality.

The difference between measured and predicted DMOS is defined as the absolute

prediction error P_{error} (equation (2.4)):

$$P_{error}(i) = \text{Score}(i) - \text{MOSp} \quad (2.4)$$

where index i denotes the image sample, while score (i) is the score given by the observer in HVT and MOSp is the predicted MOS (which is the average of all observers' scores).

e. Statistical significance analysis

The performance of VIQET as an objective IQ assessment tool was characterized by three prediction attributes: accuracy, monotonicity, and consistency. The statistical metrics RMSE, Pearson correlation, and outlier ratio together characterize the accuracy, monotonicity, and consistency of the VIQET performance. Figure 6 shows the predicted MOSp (predicted MOS) relation to MOS obtained by HVTs.

Fig. 6. MOSp relation to MOS of all images.

3. Potential PIQ Implementation in Real Applications

The results of this research on PIQ prediction have been presented to potential users in industry and academia. So far, the PIQ framework is under evaluation by several vendors of products using image processing and the IQ improvement is an essential feature of the products.

PIQ for objective image quality assessment can be implemented in smartphone industry.

Smartphone vendors gain benefits when using the PIQ assessment framework with VIQET during IQ validation. The objective and subjective IQ assessment cycles will be short and efficient (see Figs. 3, 4). The entire process of IQ assessment will be performed at home. Cost reduction of outsourcing HVTs is expected. In addition, “time to market” of new image processing features in new smartphone models will be improved.

PIQ for real time image quality assessment and improvement can be implemented in social networks.

The PIQ framework and image quality algorithms will be implemented in social networks, such as Facebook and Instagram. The block diagram in Fig. 7 illustrates the application architecture to perform real time image quality assessment and improvement of the transported images by social network members.

Fig. 7. Application architecture for real time IQ improvement in social networks.

PIQ for image quality improvement can be implemented in medical systems.

An Israeli company (ASI (Applied Spectral Imaging Ltd.)), which is a global leader in the development and sale of computer-aided imaging solutions for cytogenetics, pathology, and the life sciences, has evaluated the PIQ framework and found benefits of PIQ framework for IQ improvement of images taken by spectral imaging systems. The IQ of captured images is crucial in the analysis of regions of interest of the patient body. Better image quality means better image analysis by doctors.

The images shown in Fig. 8 are examples of the IQ improvements on the original image (raw image on the left) that helps doctors to identify the chromosomes' structure in the spectral image.

The colored images are images with different IQAs added to the original image in order to emphasize the differences between chromosomes (by adding colors to the raw black and white image).

Fig. 8. Spectral images with IQ improvement (left to right).

4. Conclusions

This research proposes a new model consisting of a framework and computer based application, the VIQET for smartphone perceived image quality prediction. The research has proven a good correlation between the results of HVTs and predicted PIQ. The procedure can be customized to particular needs, programmed and integrated into image processing, social networks, communication networks with media content, medical imaging systems, etc. in order to evaluate, predict, and improve the image quality as perceived by the users. Once the software is embedded into the user application, it can evaluate the image quality of incoming images in the gateway while the images are uploaded to the server or data bases and improve their image quality in real time. The same process is done while images are downloaded from the server or data bases.

Image quality evaluation criteria of this application have been defined according to the evaluation of perceived image quality in smartphones [6, 7, 11, 14–16].

This paper has summarized the PIQ assessment related knowledge gained from PhD research, through HVTs testing, and statistical modeling approaches for NR evaluating of PIQ and predicting it. One main conclusion that can be drawn from this paper is that the proposed model can perform remarkably well at predicting human judgments of image quality.

However, it is evident that the real time improvement of IQ is far from being solved; users have yet to develop the specific software for each case. Rather, it may seem that our current accomplishments have shown that we can design algorithms to improve image quality by more conventional applications.

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